

INTERACTION OF MOTIVES IN THE STATE OF DEVELOPMENT OF VOLITIONAL QUALITIES OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article is one of the topical problems of our time, and the importance of studying the relationship between the volitional qualities of students studying in secondary schools and the characteristics of the nervous system is noted. Also, in the psychodiagnostics activity on the study of the volitional qualities of students, the issues of the relationship of motives in the state of development of their volitional qualities were studied.*

Keywords: *will, psychodiagnostics, external and internal difficulties, motivational person, motivation, situation, person, student, success provider, mechanism function.*

In the development of our today's society, it assumes the formation of a spiritual ideal and its adoption as the main basis of the moral environment of society. Because the soul of a nation is in its decency, the root of the morality of society is a phenomenon inextricably linked with the history of the nation. Man matures from youth in the mouth of long - standing traditions, traditions. Harmony and coherence in the micro, meso and macro environments of family, neighborhood and educational institutions occupy a great place in this.

According to the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan PF-60 of January 28, 2022, the development strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, 70 of the 100 goals set for the establishment of a nationalistic state by raising human value and further developing a free civil society – In its section called improving state policy on youth, " educating youth as a person with a strong belief and outlook on life, able to resist harmful influences and currents, in the spirit of patriotism, a sense of citizenship, tolerance, respect for laws, national and universal values."marked. Uzbekistan, having gained independence, continues rapidly on the path of progress.

It is important to know that all the laws and decrees, decrees and decrees adopted by our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev are, first of all, for this country, the people and young people of the future to live a prosperous life. A special place in the development of our country, the well-being of our people is occupied by the knowledge, worldview and upbringing of young people. Because the success of reforms, the appropriate place of our state among the developed countries in the world, and above all with the development of educational development, on the other hand, the need for upbringing is also growing today, when global changes are in full swing.

Therefore, it is a necessity to form the moral consciousness of people on the principle of commonality in the context of finding out the content of democratic values. Otherwise, in the moral environment of society, the level of moral consciousness decreases. This is due to the fact that democratic values give a person literal freedom. Tries to thoroughly master the general education and professional Sciences, to understand the meaning and essence of his chosen professional direction. The fact that students have such qualities as ingenuity, perseverance, diligence plays an important role in acquiring knowledge and labor skills on the foundations of science. At the same time, it is absolutely necessary to solve complex problems and issues, mobilize volitional tension. Because without it, no result can be achieved in physical labor, in

educational activity. On the contrary, the emptiness, weakness of the will of the personality of the reader, that is, sloth, cowardice, impotence, loquacity, will lead to acquire the necessary knowledge. In our opinion, students of general education schools do not achieve high marks in the acquisition of knowledge, professional training, without the formation of volitional qualities. It should be noted separately that will is directly related to nature with the laws of general development of society, fulfilling the function of both a regulator and a driving, success-promoting mechanism.

Due to Will, a person can perform the appropriate work-action on his personal initiative, based on conscious necessity, in the direction laid down in advance in the plan and with the strength foreseen. It is also possible for a person to organize his psychic activity in a purposeful way and direct it to a certain content. The Will puts a person's behavior in the direction on the one hand, and on the other hand organizes a person's psychic activity based on existing tasks and requirements. It affects the content of personality activity. The volitional character of a person does not consist in simply fulfilling his goals, various fists. Perhaps the willful character has its own. This means that a person subjugates other motives of behavior that are not so significant for him to those goals that stand before him and are of great importance to him.

Volitional actions are done consciously, different from involuntary work-actions. In this case, the activity of the mind is manifested in the determination of the purpose of action, in the preliminary determination of the means and directions for achieving this goal, in the development of a certain decision and in the execution of this decision. Yu.A.Gorbunov points out that when will is voluntary, then he is conscious –conscious. There must be some kind of independent force between thoughts and desires on the one hand and actions on the other, and this is called willpower. A person is willing to act in accordance with or inversely with his thoughts and desires. He defined the function of the will as: "the Will can bring, end, strengthen and weaken action" it follows that when a person perceives his behavior in conscious clarity, the Will does not become associated only with mobilization and overcoming obstacles.

Will dictates the conscious control of one's own behavior, the restraint of a number of aspirations and desires. The volitional character is such that from this a person becomes self-governing, self-reliant, keeps control over his own prejudices and controls them for the rest of the time he needs them. The manifestation of Will is the activity of a person, which is a connection with the participation of consciousness in work-activities.

Methods for determining and evaluating volitional qualities are characterized by their own variety of colors. A strong will is not only to want something or achieve it, but also to force oneself to give up that desire when it is necessary.

V.K. Kalin argues that sometimes, keeping one of the human movements in check leads to the activation of the other. Researchers have been able to record phenomena in their activities, such as the characteristics of movements in normal and difficult conditions, their productivity .

The collected data analysis shows that the Will is embodied in motives, goals, self-assessment, actions, activities⁶. Therefore, willpower is the conscious control by a person of habits and actions that require overcoming external and internal difficulties.

Looking at the history of psychology, we see that with volitional qualities, the study of the relationship of personality temperament is also focused. V.K.Kalin puts forward the reasoning that the characteristics of the nervous system and temperament can affect the frequency of situations that require the emergence of a similar control, and not the effectiveness of volitional management.

But it concludes that such characteristics as calmness, enthusiasm are those that also apply to temperament. Particular attention was paid to the study of the issue of the interaction of temperament with volitional qualities, taking into account the considerations of this style. In this regard, a number of significance features were observed when the relationship between the volitional qualities of students studying in secondary schools and the features of the nervous system was studied. We have repeatedly observed this in psychodiagnostic activities on the research of the volitional qualities of students. This tradition has also been reflected in the relationship between volitional qualities and the properties of nervous processes.

Another of the tasks planned and envisaged in the study is the study of the relationship between the motivational sphere of students and volitional qualities. We intended to rely on the motivational idea of Will in the study of the connection between the volitional qualities of students and their motivations. Because the approach to Will from a motivational position is reflected in the theoretical foundations of the problem (E.Meiman, K.Levin, N.Ax, I.M.Sechenov, G.I.Chelepanov, L.S.Vigotsky, V.A.Ivannikov et al.). In our study of the connection between the volitional qualities of students and the field of motivation, V.K.We found it expedient to use the gerbacheswy methodology ("methodology for studying the degree of claim").

Y.P.Ilinn argues that when a person tries to achieve something, the idea arises in his mind that, on the one hand, the purpose of this action, on the other hand, is the action that must be carried out. This goal is achieved. Great scientist V. The choices Frankl makes are motives, not the basis of decision making. Therefore, it is not for nothing that the problem of freedom of choice is inevitable. One of the main problems of motivation and willpower - leads to the problem of conflict. The basis of motives and their, the resolution of these disputes, the freedom of choice in internal initial conflicts are most manifested. Resolving such disputes is taking the side of one of the opposing tendencies. A person needs reasons, that is, a reason, a sufficient reason, I justify. Because the decision is being made.

On the one hand it is intended to study the degree of suitability of the individual through the components of the motivational structure of the individual, on the other

from the side, the young character of the pupils is significant in that it is intended for riga. The correlation relationship between the results obtained from the application of these methods and the indicators of volitional qualities was analyzed. It would be nice if significant correlation between more volitional qualities was focused on determining the correlations between the willpower and the motivational domain of the owus. Nevertheless, an attempt was made to determine the correlational link between the volitional qualities of the students and the motivational field through methodologies of the study of will. The results obtained were considered by the general and educational stages of Secondary School students. The analysis focuses on the general state of correlative relations between the volitional qualities of students and the area of motivation. Specificities were also found in the students' indicators for general and educational stages. This allowed us to analyze the correlation relationship between the volitional qualities of readers and the indicators of the motivational sphere as follows.

It is natural that the weak development of volitional qualities, the observation of states of non-harmony between qualities, is a necessity for conducting psychocorrectional activities with students. Based on the general conclusions;

It is important that the methodologies applied on the psychodiagnostics of volitional qualities contain criteria that assess the state of connection of respondents with positive aspects of their activity, age characteristics and qualities.

Psychodiagnostics of volitional qualities of students there is an intention to study complex features or individual qualities. This makes it possible to determine in what order the issues of psychodiagnostics are carried out, the inextricably linked, diffuse and properties of the qualities under study.

In the process of researching the volitional qualities of students, it was achieved to find out whether a separate quality was formed, harmonized with other qualities, and whether a person has or does not have internality in his structure. The methodologies served to analyze and interpret volitional qualities in terms of educational stages, Educational Directions, general and private cases.

In the psychodiagnostics of volitional qualities of students, the connection of Will with the motivational sphere of the individual and the characteristics of nervous processes provides for the assessment of the state of the formation of qualities from the position of individuality. It also provides an opportunity for a psychological interpretation of the state of composition of adjectives. To do this, the use of the method of correlation analysis on the issue of relations between volitional qualities gives an effective result. So will is a unique psychic process inherent only in a person. It is reflected in the conscious actions of students. It achieves its goals by overcoming certain obstacles in the educational process of students due to will. Will has a very complex structure. The reader will be able to find strength in the implementation of their high goals in overcoming external and internal resistance.

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